

Tracing the Remains of a Disappeared Colonial Settlement. The Case of Babsa Colony

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the former Hungarian colony of Babşa through a geo-spatial and geo-historical analysis aimed at reconstructing and tracing the spatial footprint of a vanished rural settlement. Using the Hungarian colony of Babşa as a case study, the research focuses on how this temporary settlements coexisted within the landscape of a multi-ethnicity and multi-confesional landscape of Banat region, which are causes and effects of their existence as well as their gradual dissapearence. We combined historical cartography, military surveys, cadastral records and contemporary satellite imagery as well as on-site research to deepen the exploration of an ephemeral colonial-village typology in relation to its site, define its typological character and tracing its existence within its specific historical timeframe. By combining cartographic layering, field analysis and historical documentation, the study demonstrates how ephemeral settlements can be traced and spatially reconstituted despite their physical degradation or dissapearence. The Babşa Colony becomes a case study for a broader geo-historical investigation capable of identifying lost settlement typologies and understanding their role within regional territorial evolution.

Keywords: historical cartography, territorial morphology, Banat, settlement typology

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper investigates the former Hungarian colony of Babșa through a geo-spatial and geo-historical analysis aimed at reconstructing and tracing the spatial footprint of a vanished rural settlement. Situated within the Banat region, Babșa-Colony represents a specific typology of planned rural systematized settlements whose physical presence has largely disappeared. Using Babșa as a case study, the research examines how such temporary colonial settlements were established, how they functioned within the broader territorial structure of Banat and the socio-political and environmental factors contributed both to their emergence and gradual decline. The study situates Babșa-Colony in the larger context of Habsburgic colonization policies, cadastral rationalization and territorial transformation.

2 BANAT REGION

The Banat region is geographically part of Eastern Europe, but politically, it has been influenced by Central European powers, which led to a prosperous economic development that differs from other regions in Romania. The period of Austro-Hungarian rule is the stage in which historical events had the greatest impact on the evolution of the villages in rural area as a settlement typology in Banat.

2.1 History

The Austro-Hungarian domination in Banat began after the victory of the Habsburgic Empire over the Ottoman Empire, culminating in the signing of the Treaty of Passarowitz in 1718, and lasted until 1918, when, at the end of World War I, all ceded regions were unified and reintegrated into a single, unified state. The Austro-Hungarian Empire was formed by including the Kingdom of Hungary under the crown of Habsburg, but due to its autonomous status within the larger empire, the state became a dual administration system and the territories of the eastern part, including Banat, fell under the Hungarian-administered region known as Transleithania. During this period of domination, Banat, as an annexed territory, was

forced by the Hungarian administration to conform to the territorial organization and governance principles of the Austro-Hungarian Empire. This marked the beginning of the region's colonization process and the implementation of a new type of resource management, which reflected a different economic organization from the one that existed previously in the region. The dispersed organization of Romanian villages during the Middle Ages, where settlements occurred organically and spontaneously, was gradually replaced by the rigid and clean Austrian systematization and administrative organization. The implementation of strict administrative organization and the imposition of territorial configuration rules extended and shaped the morphological, cultural and social context in which the village we are studying, Babșa, was situated. Additionally, Adriana Magina, in her thesis titled *The Habsburg Religious Policy in the Banat*, describes the period of colonization as a complex religious landscape. "Orthodoxy belonged to the Romanians and Serbs living there, Catholicism was imposed by the Court in Vienna, and the Habsburg Empire's internal political struggle with the Reformation also influenced the region. As a result, in Banat, distinct churches and religious communities emerged against this backdrop of diverse religious influences. Thus, we can understand Banat's socio-cultural development as being at the crossroads of the great powers' tendencies, while still retaining a strong native presence."¹ This eclecticism is important for our study, as it offers a broader understanding of how different ethnicities and religions coexisted within the same region and where we can situate the ruin of the Catholic church, the only physical remain of the former settlement. [1-3]

2.2 Colonies

During our study, we consider not only the existence of these colonies, but its relation with the already existent village and the complementary report that was set out with the Romanian villages along the decades. The two spaces were morphologically interdependent, organized through a shared systematized grid that

¹ A. Magina, *The Habsburg religious policy in the Banat*

(1551 – 1552), pg 328 - 333

regulated parcel dimensions, street alignment, and ecclesiastical positioning. This common ground created a spatial continuity that allowed distinct settlement entities to coexist within a unified territorial logic., but keeping the autonomy of their distinct communities. We can find further the type of foreign colonies around it that survived until today, such as German Saint Michael², Moşniţa Nouă³ or colonies which had a temporary existence like Bulgarian Colony⁴, Small Topolovăţ⁵, Vucova⁶ or Iosifalau⁷. The history of these localities is similar to that of many other settlements in Banat. All of them were a dual-type of localities, composed of the Romanian-populated village to which a Hungarian colony was annexed through the colonization process imposed by the Hungarian administration. Some of them compared to others gradually disappeared, leaving behind only the footprint of its plots in the form of rows of trees and the Roman Catholic Church, which is in most cases found in a state of decadence. We can see the traces of the past in the former colony presence and preserve the memory of this space and its role in the development of the romanian village and the entire Banat region rural area. [3-4]

3 BABŞA-COLONY: HUNGARIAN SETTLEMENT

Babşa-Colony⁸ was a hungarian settlement built at the beggining of the 20th century to help the colonisation process and to exploitate the natural resources in the north-east part of the region. It was placed in the landscape of fields of crops and plain terraine, where the agriculture was the main work of it. By consulting the documents from the archives of the Romanian Catholic Diocese in Timișoara, we can establish a timeline for the

² It was one of the first settlements imposed as a colony by the Austro-Hungarian administration with two waves of colonists. The censuses attest that during the communist period the majority of the germans emigrated but village still exists today being mostly populated by romanians.

³ It is a hungarian colony established in 1903 and by the time of 1968 it became a commune that still exists and developes further today.

⁴ It was founded in 1845 as a temporary settlement to work for the hungarian owners of land in Banat on their tobacco cultivation.

⁵ Topolovăţul Mic (germ. Klein Topolovetz) was a

establishment of the colony, which aligns with the data from previous sources. (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1 Historical Timeline of the Evolution and Dissappearance of Babşa-Colony in the context of Banat's Political Transformations. Source: personal archive. (2024)

We can trace the historical evolution of the village under the influence of the Habsburg Empire by consulting the topographic surveys from the time of the territorial annexation. Thus, from the first topographic survey, which took place between 1769 and 1772, known as the Josephine Map, we can observe the presence of Babşa in the form of a village made up of scattered hamlets. The village

German colony adjoined to the commune Topolovăţu Mare in 1783 with the purpose of reinforcing the working force for the building of the the hydro-technical system on the Bega Canal.

⁶ It was a colony founded in 1807 with the slovaks to work the fields of the Ciacova area.

⁷ It was a german colony founded in 1882 but that didn't survived further as the events of the 20th century and the almost full emigration of its community left the village completely empty by 1990.

⁸ As it is mentioned in the correspondences between the people of its community and hungarian administration from Budapest

of Babşa was formed from three medieval hamlets that first appeared in 1488 under the names Upper Bapşa, Mal, and Bottom Bapşa. These hamlets united during the Ottoman domination, and in 1690, they are recorded as Bapşa and Babscha. In the 19th century it underwent a systematization process imposed by the Hungarian regime and had its streets organized based on the specific grid with houses aligned, but maintained the traditional Banat image. After the systematization, we will notice a regularization of the streets in the second topographic survey, conducted in the 19th century, in which it appears the geometric outline of the village, a morphological characteristic that still exists today. The systematized layout overlapped and reshaped the already existing villages but also determined the urban planning of the newly built, from ground-up, colonies. On the map of The third military topographic survey of the Habsburg Empire (Fig. 2) we can observe the existence of a forest in the western part of the river. Thus, this forests disappeared by 1903⁹, being cut down by the locals, and the land was allocated to the Hungarian colony that was established in that space. (Fig.3) The colony was founded in 1906 and was annexed to the already existing romanian village of that time. Thus, according to the 1899 census¹⁰, the village of Babşa had 16 Catholics and 921 Orthodox inhabitants recorded. In the 1907 census, there were 347 Catholics and 915 Orthodox inhabitants. The causes for this depopulation were multiple and wide spread for Babşa and other temporary colonies in Banat: colonialists left for better opportunities, while others were displaced by land restructuring under new governance, contributing to the colony's decline. The specific that Hungarian authority attributed to this colonies during the existance of the Empire led to their loss of purpose after the Empire's fall and the constitution of Romania's governance. [5-7]

Fig. 2 The third military survey of the Habsburg Empire, conducted between 1763 and 1887 (at a scale of 1:75,000). Source: Arcanum: maps archived digitally.

Fig. 3 A general map of Hungary from 1910. Source: Arcanum: maps archived digitally.

3.1 The colonists records

From the correspondence of the inhabitants of Babşa¹¹, we gain important insights into the social struggles and challenges that the inhabitants of the new colony had to persevere through. The letters in Hungarian reveal the name "Babşa-Colony," as it was referred to in communications from outsiders. In a formal request from a group of Hungarian locals in the Hungarian colony to the bishop it says: "We, humbly, request that His Excellency assist us in submitting a petition to the Ministry of the Interior of the Kingdom of Hungary, to allow the establishment of a school for our children in a house located on our land,

⁹ I. Ionescu, "Through Banat and through the village of Babşa, Timișoara, 2004. (pg. 60-61)

¹⁰ The data were provided by Archive of the Roman

Catholic Diocese of Timișoara

¹¹ The correspondences were provided by Archive of the Roman Catholic Diocese of Timișoara

and to grant us approval for a teacher.”¹² Another formal request to the bishop from a group of Hungarian locals in the village of Babşa, attesting to the social integration difficulties faced by the Hungarian settlers.¹³ Several inhabitants of Babşa, through their repeated requests, expressed that, since the spring of 1901, approximately 1000 Hungarian-speaking souls(...), having been colonized here by the state administration. We kindly ask you to consider that the local population, after this colonization, is facing difficulties, and it is necessary to open a school for young children, as there is a shortage of teachers. (...)The new generation desires to learn in Hungarian, as the population census still does not indicate an ethnically mixed character. The school, as in the past, can function either as a state school or as a parochial one, but it should exclusively have a Hungarian character”. This formal requests reveals a lack of hungarian-based education system in and expresses the new community's need for access to their own cultural and linguistic educational framework and shows how the colonists try to adapt and their struggle to make the new space their own. [8]

Fig. 4 Correspondences between the local community of Babsa-Colony and the Hungarian authority. Source: Archive of the Roman Catholic Diocese of Timișoara

This correspondences are important recordings of that time and helps us understand how the social

dynamics worked and how the the colonialists adapted to the new land. This insight into the life of the colonialists offers a more social realistic dimension to the colony.

3.2 Connection with the Romanian Babşa

The two villages were also separated by a river, which made their joint more dilluted as both of them kept their own space and their limits didn't meet. Despite their physical and ethnical division, they maintained a companionable relationship. We will consult the available censuses from several years to mark the demographic trajectory of the village of Babşa, from its founding to present. By doing so, we will be able to validate or invalidate the existence of a predominantly Romanian ethnic group or the homogenization of the two groups, as well as other social and religious considerations. By consulting the 1930 census¹⁴, we observe that under the section "Timiș-Torontal County", to which Babşa belongs, the following statistics were recorded: the settled population (on December 31, 1910, and December 29, 1930). In 1910, there were 1,338 inhabitants recorded, and in 1930, the population decreased slightly to 1,115. Thus, the village population declined, but not drastically. This information helps us form an understanding of how families were organized, with an average of 4 people per household.¹⁵ These details help us relate to the current situation in the village of Babşa, where, according to the 2024 census, a total of 12 families were recorded. In contrast to the village of Babşa, which was founded in 1488 and has continued to exist ever since, maintaining a permanent presence deeply rooted in Romanian territory, the Hungarian colony had a much shorter lifespan. It was established in 1906 and remained actively populated until 1977, when the census recorded a drastic decline in the Hungarian population. In 1941, the colony had 208 Hungarian inhabitants, but by 1977, only 14 remained. Today, a small community of elderly people still lives in Babşa, who remebers the old

¹² The original document, written in hungarian, had been translated by the author

¹³ The original document, written in hungarian, had been translated by the author

¹⁴ We used the data provided by the census of December 29, 1930 to display the demographic and

social situation of the Banat villages during the interwar period.

¹⁵ There were no "collective households" (which are more common in urban environments), and only 17 people lived there as "floating" residents.

colony, but none of the colonists remained there. The stories shared by the elderly form a collection of local memories that together build an enduring recollection of the colony. During our study we have been doing an on-site investigation where we gathered informations about this previous relations between the two communities through the informal interview with the elderly community from Babşa. The elderly were remembering the times when the Babsa-Colony was still existing: "they were given a house, a yard, a stable for animals, a pigsty, a garden, a house with a fenced yard and a well, everything they needed, and furniture, so everything was equipped, and that's how they were received, they built a village. The streets were straight, organized, with a well at every corner... good roads, well-maintained roads, with drainage ditches... but organized, they built a cultural center, a school, they had artesian wells, all the conditions... and a dike! For protection against floods, because that water often overflowed, coming from these hills, and here we were, Babşa...". This recollection was very rich in details and helped us form an image of what the settlement looked like. It informed a better reconstruction of the settlement's space.

4 THE REMAINS OF THE FORMER COLONY

By investigating the relevance of the physical artefacts of the former colony we can preserve the memory of this ephemeral settlement as well as its role in the development of the rural area in Banat region. Even if it lasted less than a century, this ephemeral colony had a significant impact on the development of romanian village of Babşa. By using the geo-historical method to retrace the old patterns of the settlements based on the GIS analys and the historical documentation, we could reconstruct its position in relation to the romanian Babsa-village. By overlapping the historical imaginery data and combined with the documented informatinos we could inform our visual tracing of the two settlements autonomus yet interdependent evolution. (Fig. 6)

Fig. 6 Cartographic Overlays of the systematization process in Banat rural territory. The case of Babsa and Babsa-Colony. Source: personal archive. (2024)

The tracing process therefore reveals that the colonial presence remains materially encoded in the territorial blueprint of the plain shaped by the former street layout, trees alignment and the church positioning within the former settlement.

4.1 Layout of trees

The most visible artefact is the footprint of the Hungarian lot, doubled by the existing tree pattern, which dates back at least 100 years ago.

Fig. 5 The vegetation pattern still present from the old colony. Source: Google Earth imaginery (2025)

This pattern holds an intrinsic historical value and continues to keep alive, both visually and perceptively, the memory of this lost colony. Echoing the base concept of memory in architecture, Jeff Malpas writes in an article that "Architecture cannot itself be understood unless its own connection to memory is acknowledged and articulated, and so the inquiry into the ontology of architecture must take the form of an inquiry into the relation between memory and place.(...) The very sensory properties of built forms – their shapes, structures, and materials – have a memorial character". The morphology of the settlement remained unchanged until the irreversible process of depopulation began. After the departure of the Hungarian community, it was completely abandoned. It began a slow yet steady process of degradation, with houses being destroyed, streets being covered by earth, and the church gradually falling into ruin. [9-11]

Fig. 6 Aerial view on the site of the former colony today.
Source: personal archive. (2024)

4.3 Vernacular dwellings

To gain insight into the appearance of these households, we can consider the Hungarian household from the village of Babşa, displayed in the The Banat Village Museum¹⁶, as a genuine example of vernacular housing belonging to the former colony of Babşa village. By analyzing this example, we can observe the typology of vernacular architecture featuring a porch along the longitudinal side, rooms arranged lengthwise, and walls made of adobe. Inside the dwellings, one can see the furniture of the time, the adobe floor, and adobe as a material used in wall construction. This house has a strong ethnographic essence in itself, as it reflects the

¹⁶ The Banat Village Museum, "Hungarian Household from the Village of Babşa," Timișoara.

way people were living during that period. The exopnat also resembles the courtyard of the house, where we can see a wheel and an animal annexe, showing the dimensions of their habitation. None of this houses exists on the site of the former colony today, being destroyed during the past decades due to erosion and abandon. But, we can illustrate how this former houses looked-like and recreate the atmosphere of it to understand their living conditions.[12-16]

Fig. 7 House of Babşa found at Banat Village Museum
Source: personal archive. (2025)

4.4 Ruin of Roman-Catholic church

The Roman-Catholic Church "St. Stephen" was built in 1913 as the sacred place for the Hungarian community of the new colony. It resembles a specific typology of colony-based churches that belonged to the foreign communities based in Banat region as colonialists.¹⁷ It features ghotic and neo-romanian motifs, that makes it historically valuable, but the brick tower is a defining element of this typology of Romanian-Catholic churches. Inside the tower, we can observe thin metal tie rods, which most likely date back to the period

¹⁷ See also the Roman-Catholic church of Cruceni, Ghizela, Nevrincea, Bulgarian Colony

when the church was built. The wooden structure that once supported the bell remains intact, though it is gradually deteriorating. An important element of the church's floor plan is the presence of the tower, located to the right of the main entrance on the west façade of the nave. This tower also serves as the access point to the mezzanine, which contains a set of stairs offering an authentic spatial experience up to the upper floor.

Fig. 8 Romano-Catholic Church "Sf. Stefan" in a ruin state waking up from the trees. Source: personal archive. (2024)

This church is the most enduring structure from all the built-up area of the colony. It belonged to the hungarian community and served as their own ecclesiastical space, practicing their romano-catholic religion. Today it is found in an advanced state of decay, with the roof collapsed into the nave and showing a series of cracks on the facades, but still retaining, in its ruin-state, a strong memory of a dissapeared settlements.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We can trace the presence of these lost and abandoned colonial settlements by their remanents, such elements as trees, ruins or street patterns altogheter with local stories that acknowledge their existence. Through GIS-based overlay and comparative analysis, the former colony of Babşa emerges not as a lost or purely historical entity, but as a morphologically persistent territorial imprint. Rather than interpreting absence as disappearance, the study demonstrates how GIS-based stratification can reconstruct ephemeral rural typologies and situate them within the broader geo-historical evolution of the Banat landscape.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank to the people who helped me develop this research by offering resources and support throughout this study: Ambulance for Monuments for providing the digital support for investigating the church and its site, the community of Babsa for accepting my interviews and to Daniel Burileanu Tellman, for supervising this paper and providing guidance along the research process.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Constantiniu, A Honest History of the Romanian People, ed. Univers Enciclopedic, București, 2002
- [2] A. Magina, The Hapsburg religious policy in the Banat (1551 – 1552), ed. Muze

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[3] Neumann, V. Multicultural Identities in a Europe of Regions. The case of Banat County. European Journal of Intercultural Studies, 1997

[4] R. Crețean, Banat Toponymy. A short view on the origins of

the settlements in the eastern part of Timișoara, (Review of Historical Geography and Toponomastics, vol. II), no.3-4, 2007

[5] I. Ionescu, "Through Banat and through the village of Babșa", Timișoara, 2004.

[6] Monographic Survey in Belinț

- Comune , Banat Social Institute – Crișana, Timișoara, 1938.
- [7] Reșansașmentul general al populației României din 29 decembrie 1930, Vol. 1, Ed. Institutul Central de Statistică, București, V – Splaiul Unirii 28
- [8] Documents from the Archive of the Roman Catholic Diocese of Timișoara
- [9] M. Treib, Spatial Recall : Memory in Architecture and Landscape, ed. Routledge, 2009
- [10] J. Malpas, Building Memory, INTERSTICES 13, 2012
- [11] L. Leader-Elliott, Understanding Cultural Landscapes, 2024
- [12] N. Săcărașă,

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